

MEDICAL SCIENCES

CHANGES REVEALED BY TRANSMISSION ELECTRON MICROSCOPY (TEM) IN CANDIDA ALBICANS CULTURES INOCULATED WITH OIL OF OREGANO

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Abstract

The study focused on section imaging and electron microscopic structure analysis of *Candida albicans* culture treated with oregano essential oil. In the study we used cultures of *Candida albicans* ATCC pre-treated with essential oil of oregano which were initially left for 72 h at the thermostat, in order to be inhibited by the essential oil of oregano. We took samples from this environment and treated them properly so that they could be viewed and analyzed with the transmission electron microscope.

Keywords: *Candida albicans*, osmium tetroxide, Epon 812, specimen

Abbreviations: h = hour, mm = millimeter, 1 M = molar concentration (expressed in mol/liter), ATCC = standard culture of *Candida albicans*, ATCA = trichloroacetic acid (phosphotungtic acid)

GA = glutaral - dehyde, DDSA = dodeceny succinic anhydride, NMA = methyl nadic anhydride, DMP30 = 2, 4, 6 – dimethylaminomethyl phenol, TEM = Transmission electron microscope/ transmission electron microscopy

Introduction

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM)

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) is used to produce images of a sample by illuminating the sample with electrons (eg electron beam) in vacuum and detecting the electrons transmitted through the sample. Finally, using TEM we can see the columns of atoms present in crystalline samples.

A typical transmission electron microscope consists of the following components (Figure 1):

Figure 1. Schematic representation of typical transmission electron microscope components(1)

- **Electron Cannon:** Generates the electron beam. This is usually positioned at the top of the microscope column. The electron emitter is placed in a conical Wehnelt cylinder and the beam exits through the small central hole in the top of the cone.

- **Electron column:** consists of the electron gun assembly at the top, a column filled with a set of electromagnetic lenses, the sample introduction port and pressurization chamber, and a set of apertures that can be moved in and out of the beam path. The column contents are under vacuum.

- **The electromagnetic lens system:** they give the shape of the electron beam, which circulates in a spiral trajectory. Each lens is constructed from a coil of copper wire through which electrical current is passed. There is a hole in the center through which the beam travels.

- **Sample introduction port/pressurization chamber:** is where the sample is introduced into the electron column, into the path of the high voltage electron beam. Before reaching the path of the beam, the sample must pass through the pressurization chamber, which has the role of sealing hermetically to protect the vacuum inside the electronic column.

- **Main control panel and operational controls:** the instrument can be controlled via external panels using buttons, switches and joysticks.

- **Image Capture:** At the base of the column is a viewing chamber with a window and adjustable binoculars. The image is projected on the screen in the viewing room. Binoculars are available to focus the image. The screen in the viewing room is only for producing a temporary image. To collect a permanent image, a CCD camera is inserted into the beam path. This allows the image to be collected in digital form. The exposure time can be adjusted to suit the beam parameters and control the desired image quality.

Current 3D localization **microscopy** approaches are fundamentally limited in their ability to image thick, densely labeled specimens (1).

Due to the increasing popularity of electron cryo-**microscopy** (cryoEM) in the structural analysis of large biological molecules and macro-molecular complexes and the need for simple, rapid and efficient readout, there is a persuasive need for improved detectors (2).

Electronic pneumatic injection (EPI) is a technique for dermal drug delivery, which is increasingly being used in clinical practice. Immediate cutaneous distribution was visualized using ex vivo confocal **microscopy** (EVCN) (3).

To study the immunological features of the secretion of the prostate by electron **microscopy** in patients with chronic recurrent bacterial prostatitis (4).

Conventional two-photon microscopes use photomultiplier tubes, which enable high sensitivity but can detect relatively few photons per second, forcing longer pixel integration times and limiting maximum imaging rates (5).

Understanding the effect of external conditions, temperature in particular, on novel nanomaterials is of great significance. The powerful ability of scanning

tunneling **microscopy** (STM) to characterize topography and **electronic** levels on a single molecule scale is ut (6).

Scanning probe **microscopy** (SPM) is considered one of the most powerful tools for nanoscale studies that are becoming increasingly important, and SPM has shown rapid development. Atomic force **microscopy** (AFM), in particular, is the widely used SPM system (7).

Super-resolution **microscopy** can reveal the subtle biological processes hidden behind the optical diffraction barrier (8).

Material and methods

The study was conducted between July 1, 2019 and May 20, 2020 at the Faculty of Medicine of the "Ovidius" University in Constanța.

For transmission electron microscopy (TEM) we took 2 samples from the Sabouroud medium seeded with *Candida albicans* samples, from a calibrated assortment, called ATCC; the medium was initially treated with oregano essential oil; I inserted the plate into the thermostat, at the standard temperature of 37°C; this was kept for 72 h at the thermostat (10), (11), (12).

After these 72 h in which *Candida albicans* was also inhibited by oregano oil, oil containing carvacrol (13) and thymol (14), we sectioned the necessary TEM material.

The purpose of the study was to obtain images and analyze them.

The samples from the experimental variants were processed by the JASTROW method and analyzed from an ultrastructural point of view by transmission electron microscopy through the following work steps:

- prefixing,
- fixation,
- dehydration,
- inclusion in epoxy resins.

a. Prefixation in 1M cacodylate buffer with 2.7% glutaraldehyde (GA)

The sample is immersed in 2.5% buffered GA + 2% paraformaldehyde in 0.1 M Sørensen buffer, pH 7.4. The resulting sediment is resuspended in prefixing medium consisting of 1M cacodylate buffer, 1M sucrose and 2.7% GA, at a temperature of +5°C. It is homogenized and kept at a temperature of +4°C for 2 hours. The prefixed homogenate is centrifuged at 800g, which constitutes the second centrifugation for 15 minutes, and another 10 minutes at 1300g. The operation is performed with a centrifuge with cooling. The supernatant is removed by decantation, and the sediment is sufficiently condensed, attached to the bottom of the centrifuge tube. 1M cacodylate buffer and 1M sucrose, without GA, at +4°C is placed in a watch bottle, in which the firmly detached sediment from the tube is placed. It is portioned into small specimens with a side of 0.5 mm. The washing liquid is removed and the second wash is carried out using the same procedures, which has the role of removing excess fixative.

It is very important that after pre-fixation any trace of glutaraldehyde is washed away, the residues of which will prevent the binding of osmium in the post-fixing solution. If traces of aldehydes are not removed

from the tissue, upon postfixation membrane lipids will not fix well with OsO₄ (9).

b. Fixation in 2% osmium tetroxide.

Specimens are placed in small glass tubes containing 2 ml of cold fixative medium consisting of 2% (w/v) osmium tetroxide (OsO₄) dissolved in bidistilled water. The fixing itself is done for 1 hour at +4°C. During this interval the specimens turn black due to their oxidation by the osmium tetroxide, this shows that the fixation has been well done. The fixative is slowly removed by decantation and replaced with cacodylate buffer and cold sucrose to wash and remove excess osmium. The washing operation is done 2 times with cold cacodylate buffer. Each wash takes 5 minutes.

c. Dehydration of specimens

For dehydration, I use serial baths of cold ethyl alcohol, in concentration of 30%, 50% and 70%. In each alcohol bath, the specimens are kept for 10 minutes. In this dehydration phase, the specimens are contrasted in the second bath of 70% ethyl alcohol, which contains 0.5% uranyl acetate and 1% phosphotungstic acid or trichloroacetic acid (ATCA). Contrasting is done at room

temperature for 14 h, after which the specimens are dehydrated at room temperature with ethyl alcohol in a concentration of 90%, 95% followed by 2 baths in 100% ethyl alcohol and 2 baths of propylene oxide. Each bath lasts 10 minutes.

d. Inclusion in epoxy resins

Specimens with *Candida Albicans* culture cells were placed in Epon812 - (consisting of DDSA, NMA and DMP30 as a polymerization agent) mixture 1:1 with propylene oxide. Impregnation is done at room temperature for 16 hours, after which they are taken and placed in transparent capsules. The capsules are filled with pure EPON 812 (epoxy resin), kept for 3h at room temperature and 72h in a thermostat heated to a temperature of 67 °C. At the end of polymerization, the black specimens are at the top of the capsule. The specimens thus prepared are subject to evaluation from the point of view of morphological qualities.

Fine sections were double stained with uranyl acetate and lead acetate, after which they were examined with a Tecnai T12 Microscope produced by FEI, which is located at the Faculty of Medicine of the "Ovidius" University of Constanta.

Figure 2 (a, b, c, d). Epoxy resin blocks with *Candida albicans* sample and oregano essential oil analyzed from different angles

Figure 3. Sample preparation for the electron microscope

Discussion and results

Evaluation of sections

Overall characterization was performed using photomicrographs taken at x2900- x30000. From these, I selected some representative images and later interpreted what I obtained.

Caracterizarea în ansamblu s-a efectuat utilizând microfotografiile efectuate la mărimi de x2900- x30000. Dintre acestea, am selectat câteva imagini reprezentative și ulterior am interpretat ceea ce am obținut.

Figure 4. Photomicrograph size x2900, *Candida albicans* culture inoculated with oregano essential oil. The presence of numerous vacuoles and the absence of cell organelles and nucleus can be observed

Figure 5. Photomicrograph size x4800, *Candida albicans* culture inoculated with oregano essential oil. It can be seen how the number of cells was drastically reduced following the action of oregano essential oil.

Figure 6. Photomicrograph size x6800, *Candida albicans* culture inoculated with oregano essential oil. Absence of cell organelles and nucleus can be observed.

Figure 7. Photomicrograph size x9300, *Candida albicans* culture inoculated with oregano essential oil. Cell wall and cell membrane damage can be seen.

Figure 8. Photomicrograph size x9300, *Candida albicans* culture inoculated with oregano essential oil. Cell wall and cell membrane damage can be seen.

Figure 9. Photomicrograph size x13000, *Candida albicans* culture inoculated with oregano essential oil. Cell wall and cell membrane damage can be seen.

Figure 10. Photomicrograph size x13000, *Candida albicans* culture inoculated with oregano essential oil. Cell wall and cell membrane damage can be seen.

Figure 11. Photomicrograph size x18500, *Candida albicans* culture inoculated with oregano essential oil. Cell wall and cell membrane damage can be seen.

Figure 12. Photomicrograph size x13000, *Candida albicans* culture inoculated with oregano essential oil. Cell wall and cell membrane damage can be seen.

Figure 13. Photomicrograph size x18500, *Candida albicans* culture inoculated with oregano essential oil. Cell wall and cell membrane lesions can be observed.

Figure 14. Photomicrograph size x18500, *Candida albicans* culture inoculated with oregano essential oil. Damage to the cell wall and cell membranes can be seen.

Figure 15. Photomicrograph size x23000, *Candida albicans* culture inoculated with oregano essential oil. Dissociation between the cell wall and the membrane can be seen.

Figure 16. Photomicrograph size x23000, *Candida albicans* culture inoculated with oregano essential oil. Dissociation between the cell wall and the membrane can be observed.

Figure 17. Photomicrograph size x30000, *Candida albicans* culture inoculated with oregano essential oil. Dissociation between the cell wall and the membrane can be seen.

Conclusions

Oregano essential oil can be used successfully as an antifungal for conditions caused by *Candida Albicans*. This antifungal works by dissociating the cell wall and the candida membrane due to the thymol and carvacrol in the composition. The antifungal action of oregano essential oil is irreversible and has a residual effect.

References:

- [online] <http://ammrf.org.au/>.
- Ikoma H, Kudo T, Peng Y, Broxton M, Weitzstein G., Deep learning multi-shot 3D localization microscopy using hybrid optical-electronic computing, *Opt Lett.* 2021 Dec 15;46(24):6023-6026. doi: 10.1364/OL.441743.PMID: 34913909
- Faruqi AR, Henderson R., Electronic detectors for electron microscopy. *Curr Opin Struct Biol.* 2007 Oct;17(5):549-55. doi: 10.1016/j.sbi.2007.08.014. Epub 2007 Oct 29.PMID: 17913494 Review.
- Bik L, van Doorn MBA, Biskup E, Ortner VK, Haedersdal M, Olesen UH., Electronic Pneumatic Injection-Assisted Dermal Drug Delivery Visualized by Ex Vivo Confocal Microscopy. *Lasers Surg Med.* 2021 Jan;53(1):141-147. doi: 10.1002/lsm.23279. Epub 2020 Jun 8.PMID: 32515075
- Krainii PA, Ibishev KS. *Urologiia.* , Electronic microscopy assessment of immunological disorders in the secret of the prostate in patients with chronic recurrent bacterial prostatitis, 2021 Sep;(4):68-72.PMID: 34486277 Russian
- Ching-Roa VD, Olson EM, Ibrahim SF, Torres R, Giacomelli MG., Ultrahigh-speed point scanning two-photon microscopy using high dynamic range silicon photomultipliers. *Sci Rep.* 2021 Mar 4;11(1):5248. doi: 10.1038/s41598-021-84522-0.PMID: 33664354
- Fardian-Melamed N, Eidelshtein G, Rotem D, Kotlyar A, Porath D., Temperature Dependence of the

STM Morphology and Electronic Level Structure of Silver-Containing DNA, *Small.* 2020 Feb;16(5):e1905901. doi: 10.1002/sml.201905901. Epub 2019 Dec 29.PMID: 31885142

8. Choi E, Kim A, Son H, Pyo SG. *J Nanosci Nanotechnol.*, Applications of scanning probe-atomic force microscopy in nanobioelectronics., 2014 Jan;14(1):924-31. doi: 10.1166/jnn.2014.8759.PMID: 24730309 Review.

9. Wang M, Li M, Jiang S, Gao J, Xi P. *Micron.* , Plasmonics meets super-resolution microscopy in biology., 2020 Oct;137:102916.doi:10.1016/j.micron.2020.102916. Epub 2020 Jul 15.PMID: 32688264 Review.

10. Moroianu O-N, Popescu N-D, Roşoiu N, Experimental Study on Inhibitor Effects of Substances Applied in Differential Dilutions on *Albicans Candida* Cultures, *Academy of Romanian Scientists, Annals Series on Biological Sciences*, 2018, 7, 2, 61-69.

11. Moroianu Olimpia-Nicoleta, Popescu Neludoru, Urse Alina, Gurguş Leonard & Rosoiu Natalia, Study of the action of some chemical and natural substances on *Candida albicans* cultures. *Norwegian Journal of Development of the International Science*, no 91, 2022, 34-39. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7032255>.

12. Moroianu Olimpia-Nicoleta, Popescu Neludoru, Urse Alina Raluca, Rosoiu Natalia, Study on the action of Natural Products on *Candida Albicans* Crops. *International Journal of Biomedical Engineering and Clinical Science.* Vol. 8, No. 3, 2022, pp. 27-32. doi: 10.11648/j.ijbecs.20220803.11.

13. Nostro A, Papalia T., Antimicrobial Activity of carvacrol: current progress and future prospective, *April 2012*, vol.7, no.1, pp.28-35 (8).

14. Guarda A., Rubilar J.F., Miltz J., Galatto M.J., The antimicrobial activity of microencapsulated thymol and carvacrol, *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, March 2011, vol.146, no.2., pp.144-150.